

Popular Article

Animal Hostel-A New Concept

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Abstract

Animal hostel is a unique Comprehensive–Collaborative–Cooperative approach towards sustainable rearing of livestock which can be utilized as much as possible in large cities. This concept will not only help in reducing poverty but also lead to integrated livestock management. As there is minimum initial investment and there is major advantage of getting good quality milk as well as their products, it should be promoted at national level. The concept is pro-poor and pro-women along with eco-technology base with economic as well as social returns

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Introduction

The animal hostel is a place where the cattle of the village/city are kept and maintained together and have all necessary infrastructure facilities to take care of them. It has been conceptualized as a sustainable management mode. This concept is adequately fits into urban scenario. It is an opportunity to invest their money in dairy animals for unadulterated milk, which are then reared on their behalf at Animal Hostel. These should be built on the outskirts of every metropolitan city. Transparency is the USP of this concept as cows are being fed accordingly to her milk yielding capacity so we know exact feeding and management cost such data allows our investors to evaluate return on their investment. India's first animal hostel was inaugurated by Prime Minister Sh. Narendra Modi in Akodara village of Sabarkantha district (Gujrat). It is the revolutionary move in the livestock-rearing history of the nation.

Aim of Animal Hostel:

- Reduction of Drudgery of Women Folk
- Collective Village Resource Management
- Improvement of Human Health
- Better Management of Dung and Urine
- Hygienic Environment
- Integrated Animal Care
- Production of Gobar Gas
- Production of Organic Manures

Advantages of Animal Hostel

- Production of Unadulterated milk of own cow or buffalo which is easy to digest and best for new born baby and old aged member of family
- Minimum investment
- Invest for once and earn for long time
- Anytime can sell their cow
- Monthly transfer of money generated by extra milk/processed milk
- Proper documentation of animal between owner and cow hostel in charge
- Risk is minimum as animals will be insured under government scheme
- Cow dung and urine can also be used for making organic manure and running gohar gas plants to generate money for maintaining such hostels
- Protection of cows and conservation of indigenous breeds
- Paucity of space doesn't allow anyone to keep cows in cities

A pregnant/milk yielding cow/buffalo will be bought by investors from farmers and then pay a small fee each month for their cow to be looked after. In return owner can get milk from cows & to generate revenue can sell raw milk/paneer/ghee/butter-milk to available customers. This concept is aimed at people who have some money to invest for profit and unadulterated milk. People want to have own animals but don't have the land, time and skills to rear the cows. The facilities in the hostel include in house fodder production, fodder storage, electricity generation through bio gas plants, vermin compost production, milk collection room, veterinary service centre and a water storage tank.

Beneficiaries have to pay specific amount per animal. Recipient will keep their allotted area neat and clean. The recipients will collect cow dung and dump it in to gohar gas plant unit. Slurry of this gohar gas unit is being used for the vermin compost unit. The produce of these vermin compost units are used as an organic fertilizer to increase agriculture production and improved soil quality, which generates an additional income.

Comprehensive–Collaborative-Cooperative Model

The Animal Hostel Project is unique in terms of its concept of vertical and horizontal integration and participation. It is a Comprehensive model which includes integration of animal husbandry, pasture development, renewable energy and ecofriendly technology, organic farming and Biometrics based animal identification. It is a good collaborative model with participation by various departments/agencies of Government, Panchayat Raj institutions and Milk Co-operative Societies. What is unique to this project is that the village level institutions i.e., Village Milk Cooperative Society, and Gram Panchayat are the key stake holders in development of the Animal Hostel. This project also provides a good example of cooperation in terms of participation of all stakeholders in provision of

technical & financial inputs. It can be managed by Village milk co-operative society, which in turn would create a good model of people's participation in managing personal and community resources with Government help. It is expected that the role of the Government will become over time more and more an enabling one and the model will become self-sufficient and scale able.

Eco-Technology

Eco technologies are the tools for sustainable management of the local resources with pro-nature orientation and participation of all level people with the idea of conservation of natural resources. It is a good example of an "Eco-technology" model due to its uniqueness in people's participation, creation of alternate sources of energy, integration of animal husbandry & crop husbandry practices, reduction in use of non-renewable energy sources, promotion of organic farming, employment generation, reduction in carbon footprint and other activities, these activities put together ensure that the hostel is a sustainable model towards achieving the objectives of the project.

Pro-Poor/Pro-Woman

Another unique feature of the Animal Hostel is that the project is women centric and works for the poor families. Animal hostel project will reduce drudgery of women in regular animal care activities and provide alternate options for their involvement in other livelihood development activities. Extra facilities and benefits have been given to BPL families of the village without any differentiation in care of animals in the hostel at lower participatory cost. This Pro-Poor and Pro-Women model will help in achieving the development of the village which is equitable and aims at economic and social justice.

Returns

The Animal Hostel gives multiple returns such as direct economic returns, improvement in social conditions and better environment management. Though this is a new venture and the data is too recent to allow for a comparative analysis, certain inferences can be drawn.

Conclusion

The animal hostel project is therefore a revolutionary step in cooperative management of livestock as well as conservation of natural resources with its unique model of integration, cooperation and conservation.

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